

Questionnaire for Energy Efficiency

The following questionnaire is a crucial phase of this study which has as main object the development of an integrated vulnerability tool addressing flood risk, seismic risk, landslide risk and building energy efficiency.

This tool should be able to indicate what the overall vulnerability of a building is, for the purpose of more effective management of interventions.

The developed methodology that can be valid for:

- residential building typology present in Algeria, and in particular for the area of the Wadi Abiod Valley;
- buildings with features similar to the one present in Algeria located in areas of the Globe subject to seismic, flood, and landslide risks, where targeted interventions for energy efficiency need to be implemented.

For the purpose of this assessment, individual vulnerabilities (called V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E in the diagram below) will first be assessed.

At the preliminary stage of the study, based on the relevant literature, the main factors affecting individual vulnerabilities toward seismic, flood, landslide risks and energy efficiency were identified. Then, these factors have been expertly grouped into categories.

With this questionnaire, we ask you, as experts, to give a weight to the individual vulnerability factors and categories that is representative of the factor or category importance in defining the total vulnerability of the building.

For clarity, the diagram below summarizes the steps identified for the individual vulnerability assessment.

Once the weights to each category and factor have been determined, the weight of the individual factor will be given by the product of the weight of the category and the weight of the factor within that category.

In particular, the individual vulnerability of the building (V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E) will be given by the following formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_i * \sum_{j=1}^m p_{i,j} * v_{i,j}$$

Where:

- P_i is the weight of the category i
- $p_{i,j}$ is the weight of the factor j within category i
- $v_{i,j}$ is the value of the factor j within category i (appropriately reclassified on a scale from 0 to 1)
- n is the total number of categories.
- m is the total number of factors within each category

Finally, the individual vulnerabilities for each risk will be integrated based on their respective hazards. This integration will allow for a comprehensive understanding of the building's overall vulnerability profile. The result can be used by decision-makers to prioritize mitigation efforts and allocate resources effectively to enhance the resilience of the building against various hazards.

Instructions for Questionnaire Completion

In what follows, you will first be provided with a description of the individual categories and the related factors identified for your risk. Then, you will be provided with an outline where you can provide your judgment and any comments and/or suggestions.

The following steps are recommended for completing the questionnaire:

1. First read the entire questionnaire, without thinking about assigning any values. This step serves to gain an overview of the problem in all its components.
2. Carefully reread the definitions of categories and factors.
3. Only then to associate a weight with each category (P_i), such that the sum of the category weights is equal to 1.
4. Next, we ask you to associate a weight ($p_{i,j}$) to the factors contained in each category, according to the criterion that within each category the sum of the weights should be equal to 1.

Note: in the COMMENTS section you should enter reason for choosing a weight value, whereas, in the SUGGESTIONS section you should enter eventual suggestions of any kind, including changes that you deem necessary (e.g., other factors to be considered, factors to be neglected, how the define the factor, etc...).

IT IS IMPORTANT THAT ANY CHOICES OR COMMENTS BE ARGUED, SO THAT THIS INFORMATION CAN BE PROVIDED TO THE POOL OF EXPERTS INVOLVED, WHO MAY MODIFY OR CONFIRM THEIR INITIAL JUDGMENT, AT A SECOND STAGE OF THE INVESTIGATION.

ENERGY VULNERABILITY INDEX

Category 1: Typological characteristics

This category encompasses the factors characterizing the structure of the building in terms of area/volume ratio, number of floors and windows to walls ratio.

Weight Category 1 (P1)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Performance characteristics

This category includes the building's construction characteristics that have an impact on its energy performance, such as wall and floor coverings, types of fixtures, sunscreens, etc.

Weight Category 2 (P2)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Plant engineering

The following category considers all aspects of plant engineering, relating to the types of installations and emission terminals, both domestic water heating and air conditioning systems, as well as sources from renewable sources, etc.

Weight Category 3 (P3)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 1: Typological characteristics

- **Surface-to-Volume Ratio**

This factor basically indicates how compact the building is (and therefore inherently more energy efficient)

Weight Factor 1 (p ₁₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Number of floors**

Means the number of floors above ground.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₁₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Windows to wall ratio**

The window to wall ratio is an index that identifies air-to-light ratios.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₁₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Performance characteristics

- **External wall stratification**

This factor defines how the stratification of walls that have one side facing outwards is composed (e.g., massive/light insulated/non-insulated structures).

Weight Factor 1 (p ₂₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Stratification of slabs towards the outside or unheated rooms**

This factor defines how the layering of slabs corresponding to external areas or unheated rooms of the building (e.g., massive/light insulated/non-insulated structures) is composed.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₂₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **External wall cladding**

This refers to the color (light or dark) of the external cladding.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₂₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Type of window frames**

This factor defines the technical characteristics of window frames, both glazing and supports (frame, single/double glazing, with or without thermal break).

Weight Factor 4 (p24)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Solar shading**

By solar shading we mean here the presence or absence of fixed or movable screens that protect the interior of the house from the direct action of the sun's rays.

Weight Factor 5 (p25)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Installations

- **Type of emission terminals**

By emission terminals we mean the type of terminal used to emit heat into the environment (e.g., radiators, fancoils, etc...)

Weight Factor 1 (p31)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Type of system regulation**

The type of system regulation refers to whether the system is controlled by a thermostat, on-off system or via climate regulation.

Weight Factor 2 (p32)	
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Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Type of DHW production system**

Mainly the modes of Domestic Hot Water production are electric, or fossil-fuel fired boiler, solar thermal system and heat pump.

Weight Factor 3 (p33)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **The presence of installations powered by renewable sources.**

This factor defines whether there are installations powered by renewable sources, and if so, how much power is generated per housing unit.

Weight Factor 4 (p34)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Type of heat generator**

The heat generator can take the form of boilers (traditional fuel-fired or fuel-fired condensing)

Weight Factor 6 (p35)	
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Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Summer air-conditioning system**

This factor indicates, if there is one, what type of summer air-conditioning system is present in the building (e.g., split for each flat, centralised cooling unit, etc...)

Weight Factor 7 (p ₃₆)	
Comments	
Suggestions	